

Genotype x environment interaction analysis in Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.)

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Original Research Article Received on March 20, 2020 Revised on March 29, 2020 Accepted on April 18, 2020 Published on April 27, 2020</p> <p>Article Authors Dipendra Rawal, Amit Tomar, Mahak Singh</p> <p>Corresponding Author Email tomarcsa@gmail.com</p>	<p>The results of genotype x environment interaction analysis revealed highly significant mean squares due to genotypes as well as environments for all the characters which indicated presence of substantial differences among the genotypes as well as environments for all the eleven characters. The environment linear (E-L) component was also significant for all the characters indicating that the six environments can be graded linearly for their differences in influencing the expression of characters of wheat genotypes. The mean squares due to genotype x environment interaction were also highly significant for all the characters except days to heading, plant height, effective tillers per plant and total number of tillers per plant to suggest important role of g x e interaction in expression of most of the characters in wheat. The linear component of g x e interaction was significant for all the characters which indicated good possibility of predicting linear responses of genotypes for all the characters under study. Thus, there would be ample possibility of discriminating the genotypes for above average, below average and average linear responses to predict their performances in changing environments under study. The significance of non-linear component (pooled deviation) of g x e interactions for all characters except ear length suggested that considerable number of genotypes may exhibit unpredictable and unstable mean performance for different characters across environments even defying their prediction on the basis of linear sensitivity coefficient.</p>
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Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L. em. Thell) is the second most important staple food crop of the world after rice. However, it is cultivated more widely around the world than rice due to wide adaptation and greater role in human nutrition as well as in agricultural economy. Wheat is consumed in a variety of ways such as bread, chapatti, porridge, flour, suji etc. Wheat has relatively high content of niacin and thiamin which are principally concerned in providing the special protein called 'Gluten'. Wheat proteins are of special significance because Gluten provides the framework of spongy cellular texture of bread and baked products.

India has become self sufficient in meeting wheat grain consumption of its population at present but substantial increase in wheat production will be required to provide food security to the ever increasing population of our country. The population of India is likely to reach around 1.3 billion by the year 2020. Thus, the huge target of increasing wheat production by about 35 million tonnes within two decades is a big challenge that cannot be met only by increasing the area under production and improving the production technology until and unless the genetic potential of wheat varieties for different areas and environments is enhanced considerably.

Materials and Methods

The experimental material for the study comprised of 50 exotic and indigenous germplasm lines of wheat collected from different coordinating units of All India Coordinated Wheat Improvement Project (AICWIP). These genotypes exhibited wide spectrum of variation for various agronomical and morphological characters. The experiments were laid out in augmented block design during rabi 2013-14. Each plot consisted of two rows of 3 m length with a spacing of 5 cm within the rows and 25 cm between the rows. Recommended cultural practices were followed to raise good crop. The data was recorded on five randomly selected plants from each replication leaving the border plants from all the four sides, in order to avoid the sampling error. Readings from five plants was averaged replication-wise and the mean data was used for the statistical analysis for 11 characters namely, days to flowering, plant height (cm), number of effective tillers per plant, ear length (cm), number of spikelets per spike, number of grains per spike, days to maturity, test weight (g), harvest index (%), biological yield per plant (g) and grain yield per plant (g).

Results and Discussion

The study of genotype x environment (g x e) interaction was carried out following (Eberhart and Russell, 1996). The pooled analysis of variance for g x e interactions in respect of different characters of 64 genotypes across six environments is set out in table-1. The mean squares due to genotypes were highly significant for all the eleven characters under study. The variances due to environments and environment linear (E-L) component were also highly significant for all the characters. Therefore, highly significant differences were present among genotypes as well as environments for all the characters under study. The g x e interaction component was highly significant for all the characters except days to heading, plant height, effective tillers per plant and total number of tillers per plant. The linear component of g x e interaction was preponderant in case of all the characters. The non-linear component of g x e interaction (pooled deviation) assumed significance in all the cases except ear length. The mean performance and stability parameters of 64 wheat genotypes in respect of eleven characters across six

environments are presented in table 1. The character-wise description is given below:

Days to Heading

The linear as well as non-linear components of g x e interaction were significant for expression of this character. Two entries, UP-2700 and J-501 possessed $b > 1$, while eight genotypes, namely, NIAW-1417, PBW-154, PBW-373, PBW-443, PBW-502, RAJ-3077, DBW-22 and HD-2204 exhibited $b < 1$. Remaining fifty-four genotypes were characterized by $b = 1$. The non-linear sensitivity coefficients (S^2di) of nineteen entries were greater than zero. The S^2di values of rest of the entries did not deviate significantly from zero. The earliest heading genotype, HALNA, possessed $b = 1$ and $S^2di > 0$. The other early heading genotypes, WR-1743, HP-1633, GW-9712, GW-9715 and NW-1014 were characterized by $b = 1$ and $S^2di = 0$.

Plant Height

The linear as well as non-linear components of the g x e interaction were significant for this character. Five genotypes, NW-1014, PBW-154, WR-1743, WH-1022 and HP-1633 showed $b > 1$, while RAJ-3077, RAJ-3765, HP-1744 and HD-2733 were characterized with $b < 1$. Remaining 54 entries had $b = 1$. The non-linear sensitivity coefficients of 37 genotypes were greater than zero, while S^2di values of rest of the entries (27) did not deviate significantly from zero. The shortest genotype, DBW-22 had $b = 1$ and $S^2di = 0$. Among the five shorter entries following DBW-22, the genotypes, GW-9712, HI-8498 and NIAW-1342 possessed $b = 1$ and $S^2di = 0$ to appear as average responsive and stable genotypes of short stature along with DBW-22.

Effective Tillers per Plant

The linear and non-linear components of g x e interaction were significant for effective tillers per plant. Seven entries, PBW-443, UP-2003, DL-784-3, HD-2329, HD-2824, HDR-77 and HI-1539 exhibited $b > 1$ while two genotypes, NW-1014 and PBW-373 recorded $b < 1$. Thus, remaining 55 genotypes had $b = 1$. Seven out of 64 entries exhibiting $S^2di > 0$ were RAJ-3077, RAJ-4077, UP-2003, WH-1022, GW-9712, HD-2824 and HALNA, while remaining 57 genotypes showed $S^2di = 0$.

Among the lines having very high mean performance for this character, RWP-2004-2, DBW-14, FKW-1 and NW-1012 showed $b=1$ and $S^2di=0$, while NW-1014 had $b<1$ and $S^2di=0$.

Total Number of Tillers per Plant

The linear as well as non-linear components of $g \times e$ interaction were significant for this character. Six genotypes, UAS-281, WH-1021, DL-784-3, HD-2329, HD-2824 and HDR-77 possessed $b>1$ while remaining 58 genotypes were characterized with $b=1$ as none of the entries had $b>1$. The non-linear sensitivity coefficients of four genotypes, namely, WH-1022, DBW-11, HDR-77 and HALNA were greater than zero so that remaining 60 entries were characterized with $S^2di=0$. The four lines of top non-significant group having high mean performance for total number of tillers per plant, NW-1012, NW-1014, RWP-2004-2 and FKW-1 possessed $b=1$ and $S^2di=0$.

Days to Maturity

The linear as well as non-linear components of $g \times e$ interaction were significant for this character. Five genotypes, GW-9712, HP-1633, HD-2285, HI-1539 and HALNA showed $b>1$ while ten genotypes, NW-1012, PBW-154, PBW-343, PBW-443, RAJ-3777, UP-2003, UP-2338, WH-1021, WH-1022 and J-501 showed $b<1$. The remaining 49 entries had $b=1$. The non-linear sensitivity coefficients of eighteen genotypes, *viz.*, PBW-343, DBW-262, UP-2003, UP-2338, WH-1031, AKW-381, DBW-11, DBW-22, DBW-31, FKW-1, GW-9712, GW-9715, HD-2205, HD-2307, HDR-77, HUW-6468, HALNA and J-501 were greater than zero while remaining 46 genotypes had $S^2di=0$. Among the early maturing genotypes, NW-1076, WR-1743, DBW-14, HP-1744 and HUW-234 possessed $b=1$ and $S^2di=0$ while HP-1633 and HD-2285 showed $b>1$ $S^2di=0$. HALNA had $b>1$ and $S^2di>0$ while J-501 showed $b<1$ and $S^2di>0$.

Ear Length

Only linear component of $g \times e$ interaction was significant for ear length. Fifteen genotypes, PBW-443, RAJ-3077, RAJ-3765, RAJ-3777, RAJ-4077, UP-2338, WH-1022, HP-1633, HP-1761, HD-2204, HD-2824, HDR-77, HI-1539, HS-240 and HUW-268 possessed $b>1$ while statistically lower than unity linear sensitivity coefficient was

exhibited only by FKW-1 and HD-2329. The remaining 47 genotypes were characterized by $b=1$. The non-significance of non-linear component of $g \times e$ interactions appeared responsible for resulting S^2di values of 60 out of 64 entries equal to zero, while the four genotypes, NW-1067, HS-240, HUW-234 and J-501 showed $S^2di>0$. The entry exhibiting longest ears, UP-2699, had $b=1$ and $S^2di=0$. Among the lines exhibiting very high mean performance for ear length, UP-2697, NIAW-1342, AKW-381, WH-1021, WR-881, UP-2700 and HD-2733 exhibited $b=1$ and $S^2di=0$ while, WH-1022, UP-2338 and Raj-3777, showed $b>1$ and $S^2di=0$.

Number of Grains per Spike

The linear as well as non-linear components of $g \times e$ interaction were significant for this character. The linear sensitivity coefficients of 15 genotypes *viz.*, NW-1067, NW-1076, NIAW-1342, NIAW-1417, PBW-154, PBW-343, RAJ-3077, RAJ-3777, RAJ-4077, RWP-2004-2, FKW-1, GW-9712, HP-1633, HP-1761 and KC-975, were greater than unity of while thirteen genotypes, namely, PBW-443, UP-2003, UP-2699, UP-2700, UAS-281, VW-486, WR-784-4, WR-1695, DBW-22, DL-784-3, HP-1744, HS-240 and J-501 had linear sensitivity coefficients lesser than unity. Remaining 36 genotypes were characterized by $b=1$. The non-linear sensitivity coefficients of 28 entries were greater than zero and remaining 36 entries had $S^2di=0$. Among the genotypes having very high mean performance for number of grains per spike, UP-2003 and NIAW-1342 showed $b>1$ and $S^2di=0$ while NW-2036 exhibited $b=1$ and $S^2di=0$.

Test Weight

The linear as well as non-linear components of $g \times e$ interaction were significant for this character. Fifteen entries, PBW-343, PBW-443, RAJ-4077, UP-262, UP-2697, UP-2699, UP-2700, WR-1695, WH-1022, RWP-2004-2, AKW-381, DBW-22, DBW-31, KC-975 and J-501 possessed $b>1$ while NW-1076, NW-2036, PBW-373, RAJ-3077, UP-2425, VW-486, HP-1633, HD-2204, HD-2285 and HUW-234 had $b<1$. The remaining 39 genotypes showed $b=1$. The non-linear sensitivity coefficients of 10 genotypes *viz.*, UP-2003, VW-486, AKW-770, DBW-31, HP-1731, KC-975, HDR-77, NI-1539, HALNA and J-501 were greater than zero to indicate their unstable nature in expression of test weight.

Table 1. Pooled analysis of variance for 11 characters across six environments

Source of variation	d. f.	Days to heading	Plant height (cm)	Effective tillers/ plant	Total number of tillers/ plant	Days to maturity	Ear length (cm)	Number of grains/ spike	Test weight (g)	Harvest index (%)	Biological yield/plant (g)	Grain yield/ plant (g)
Rep. within Env.	123.00	3.71	5.77	0.91**	1.63**	2.95	0.29**	1.29	4.48**	7.52	3.15	0.76**
Varieties	63.00	121.20**	221.93**	0.41**	0.33**	49.36**	3.31**	90.36**	9.93**	96.33**	17.91**	1.57**
Env. + (Var.*Env.)	320.00	34.44**	20.51**	0.31**	0.26**	67.91**	0.31**	14.06**	9.09**	56.67**	4.24**	1.75**
Environments	5.00	1968.01**	788.91**	9.89**	6.40**	4145.00**	6.67**	474.86**	379.49**	1163.83**	112.70**	80.18**
Var.*Env.	315.00	3.75	8.31	0.16	0.16	3.20**	0.21**	6.75**	3.21**	39.10**	2.52**	0.50**
Environments (Lin.)	1.00	9840.05**	3944.53**	49.46**	32.01**	20724.99**	33.33**	2374.32**	1897.44**	5819.16**	563.50**	400.92*
Var.*Env. (Lin.)	63.00	6.12**	13.75**	0.27**	0.21*	9.06**	0.61**	19.18**	8.64**	77.05**	5.03**	1.44**
Pooled Deviation	256.00	3.11**	6.84**	0.13**	0.15**	1.70**	0.11	3.58**	1.82**	29.14**	1.86**	0.27**
Pooled Error	756.00	1.10	1.72	0.09	0.12	0.86	0.10	1.10	1.08	3.16	0.52	0.15
Total	383.00	48.71	53.64	0.33	0.27	64.86	0.81	26.61	9.23	63.19	6.49	1.72

*, ** significant at 5% and 1% probability levels

Among the genotypes exhibiting higher test weight, WR-1695, UP-2425 and HUW-234 showed $b>1$ and $S^2di=0$ while Raj-3765 and HD-2643 exhibited $b=1$ and $S^2di=0$. DBW-31 had $b>1$ and $S^2di>0$ while HALNA showed $b=1$ and $S^2di>0$.

Harvest Index

The linear as well as non-linear components of $g \times e$ interaction were significant for harvest index. Seven genotypes, NIAW-1342, PBW-343, PBW-443, RAJ-3077, RAJ-3965, UP-2699 and GW-9712 possessed $b>1$ while only one genotype, HALNA, emerged with $b<1$. Remaining 56 entries were characterized by $b=1$. Fifty-two of the 64 genotypes exhibited $S^2di>0$ while the twelve genotypes possessing $S^2di=0$ were NW-1014, NW-2036, PBW-343, UP-262, WH-1021, WH-1022, DBW-22, GW-9712, HP-1744, HS-240, HUW-468 and HALNA.

Biological Yield per Plant

The linear as well as non-linear components of $g \times e$ interactions were significant for this character.

Nine genotypes, PBW-154, UP-2697, UP-2699, UAS-281, VW-486, WR-881, WR-1743, WH-1021 and HP-1633 possessed $b>1$ while none of the genotypes were found to exhibit $b<1$. The remaining 55 genotypes were characterized by $b=1$. Thirty out of 64 genotypes exhibited $S^2di>0$ while 34 genotypes showed $S^2di=0$. Among the entries exhibiting higher mean performance for biological yield per plant, WR-881 and HP-1633 had $b>1$ and $S^2di=0$ while RAJ-4077, AKW-381, HD-2329 and HS-240 showed $b=1$ and $S^2di=0$. WR-783-4, WH-2045 and RWP-2004-2 recorded $b=1$ and $S^2di>0$.

Grain Yield per Plant

The linear as well as non-linear components of $g \times e$ interaction were significant for grain yield per plant. Ten genotypes, NW-1012, PBW-343, PBW-443, UP-2699, UP-2700, WR-783-4, RWP-2004-2, PBW-31, HD-2733 and HI-1539 emerged with $b>1$ values while NW-1014, NW-1076, UP-262, WR-1743, WH-2045, PBW-14, GW-9715, HD-2285, HD-2643, HUW-234 and HALNA recorded $b<1$.

The remaining 42 genotypes were characterized by $b=1$. The twelve entries exhibiting $S^2di>0$ were NW-1012, NW-1076, NIAW-1342, PBW-502, UP-2697, WR-783-4, WR-1695, WH-1021, WH-1031, FKW-1, HP-1731 and HD-2733. The remaining 52 genotypes were characterized by $S^2di=0$. Among the genotypes exhibiting higher grain yield per plant, WR-881, AKW-381, DL-784-3, PBW-154, HS-240 and J-501 possessed $b=1$ and $S^2di=0$ while WH-2045 had $b>1$ and $S^2di=0$. However, FKW-1 showed $b=1$ and $S^2di>0$. These findings were also similar to (Beale, 1969, Korkut *et al.*, 2001, Khan *et al.*, 2005, Verma *et al.*, 2006, Singh and Sharma, 2007, Singh *et al.*, 2008, Tila *et al.*, 2008, Dharmendra *et al.*, 2010).

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